

LAND DEVELOPMENT BY FLIPPING AND HUMP & HOLLOWING

AN UPDATED GUIDE FOR WEST COAST FARMERS 2015

Ministry for Primary Industries
Manatū Ahu Matua

Plant & Food
RESEARCH
RANGAHAU AHUMĀRA KAI

 Westland Milk Products
Hokitika - New Zealand

*Dairy***NZ**

Profitability. Sustainability. Competitiveness.

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FOREWORD

This guide has been prepared by Abie Horrocks and Steve Thomas, The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited, and Murray Craighead, Nutrient Solutions Limited. It updates the previous guide 'Land Development by Flipping and Humping & Hollowing' 2006, prepared by Murray Craighead, Nutrient Solutions Limited, and Richard Reynolds, formally of Dexcel.

This revised guide presents key findings from recent projects as well as current information on land development provided by experienced farmers, contractors, researchers, councils and dairy industry groups (such as Westland Milk Products Limited and Landcorp New Zealand). It offers West Coast farmers the most up to date information to support land development.

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Photographs have been supplied by Craig Ross, Landcare Research Limited; Abie Horrocks, The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited; Murray Craighead, Nutrient Solutions Limited; Chris Pullen, Westland Milk Products Limited; and the West Coast Regional Council.

We hope this information will assist farmers and contractors when making decisions about land development.

DISCLAIMER

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CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

Drainage is the main limitation to production on many West Coast soils. Plant growth becomes limited due to lack of aeration caused by waterlogging of soils. Waterlogging is a function of the amount of rainfall and the ability of the land to quickly release that water. The role of soil hydrology and land drainage is important.

This guide is designed to help farmers make well informed land development decisions. It provides the information needed to identify the best land to develop, the likely agronomic and financial benefits to your farm operation, the planning and environmental considerations required, how to carry out the development and the follow-up work to maintain long-term productivity.

1.1. FLIPPING

Flipping is the inversion and mixing of soil deep enough to break up iron pans that are impeding drainage. It enables water to drain vertically through the soil profile. Several iron pans may be broken in the process and stones may be brought up and incorporated into the surface soil. The resulting surface either follows natural contours (contouring) or is levelled flat.

1.2. HUMP & HOLLOWING

Hump & hollowing is designed to enhance surface runoff and to a lesser extent vertical drainage. The hollow is usually dug to the depth of the top iron pan (to give a firm base), and excavated soil is humped on the adjacent area. The elevated hump sheds water into the hollow or pilot drain. This sequence is repeated across the paddock.

Over time new or tailored hump & hollowing approaches have developed. Trenching and flipping of material on the lower slopes and hollows breaks the pans and helps overcome “weep lines” and wet hollows. Following natural contours requires less excavation while utilising existing drainage channels (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Drainage channels on contoured land.

CHAPTER 2. UNDERSTANDING WEST COAST SOILS

West Coast soils largely fit into three groups:

Recent soils are young alluvial soils formed alongside rivers or on young fans. Some Recent soils along rivers require little drainage (i.e. Karamea soils and Hokitika soils). Karangarua gley soils are slow draining and require drainage. Other Recent soils along rivers are seasonally wet and require some drainage (i.e. Harihari soils).

Brown soils were formed on generally lower terraces and are older and more weathered than Recent soils. Coarser Brown soils on the lower alluvial terraces (e.g. Ahaura soils) are free draining and need little modification. Imperfectly drained Ikamatua Brown soils are wet for some of the year and may require hump & hollowing or contouring.

Podzolised soils (e.g. Pakihi soils) are wet, infertile and strongly weathered. The term Pakihi refers to the type of marshy vegetation (e.g. rushes, sedges and stunted manuka). They occur on both the lower and high terraces and are over 10,000 years old. They are poorly drained due to impermeable iron pans and cemented gravels at varying depths. To improve vertical drainage subsoil pans must be broken up by either flipping or hump & hollowing. Where there is coarse material that won't reconsolidate, such as with iron sand podzols (Figure 2), flipping is the most suitable development method. Where there is already a slope to work with, contouring may be appropriate.

Some podzols are stony to the surface (Figure 3), while others consist of fine textured material over stones (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Older inland dunes suit flipping due to the coarse material that is less likely to reconsolidate (photo courtesy of Craig Ross, Landcare Research Ltd).

Figure 3. Soil profile showing iron pan and stones to the surface.

There are also small pockets of **peat** in coastal and inland depressions. Peaty soils can be difficult to develop as they have no structure and retain a lot of water. If shallow the stony subsoil may be mixed with the peat. If deep, it may be better left undeveloped.

Figure 4. High organic matter retains water and impedes drainage.

2.1. REGIONAL VARIATIONS IN DRAINAGE REQUIREMENTS

Table 1. Regional variations in drainage requirements.

Region	Soil type and drainage requirements
Coastal	Mostly sandy soils, e.g. Okari soils, occur along the coast of Buller and Westland. Often associated with organic peat soils in the depressions behind the dunes (e.g. Kini soils).
Karamea	Apart from coastal sands and peats, most farming is on Recent free draining Karamea and slower draining, poorly aerated (gleyed) Karangarua soils that need some drainage. Above these on the terraces are Kongahu Pakihi soils, which are poorly drained. Similar soils are present in Golden Bay along with some Brown Ahaura soils (see Grey Valley comments).
Westport Cape Foulwind Charleston	Coastal sands and Recent soils are along the rivers. Lower terraces are often Charleston marine and dune sands, while higher terraces are stonier shallow soils (e.g. Addison soils). Both are Pakihi soils and lend themselves to flipping or hump & hollowing.
Grey Valley Inangahua Valley	Along the rivers are recent well-drained Hokitika soils that need little or no draining and seasonally wet Harihari soils that benefit from development. Coarser Brown soils on the lower terraces towards the rivers (e.g. Ahaura soils) need little modification. Upper terrace soils, such as Okarito and Mawhera Pakihi soils, require drainage such as flipping or hump & hollowing. Ikamatua and gleyed Maimai soils are wet for much of the year requiring hump & hollowing or contouring.

Region	Soil type and drainage requirements
Brunner Taramakau	Large areas of gleyed Recent Harihari soils. Ikamatua Brown soils are common on the terraces (see Grey Valley comments). Bell Hill and Inangahua have Pakihi soils that are sandy or peaty in places.
Hokitika Kokatahi Kowhitirangi	Large areas of Recent soils; free draining Hokitika soils and slower draining gleyed Karangarua soils. Sandy coastal soils and terrace Pakihi soils are common north of Hokitika and many have already been hump & hollowed.
Ross to Whataroa	Most farming is on Recent soils; free draining Hokitika soils and slower draining gley Recent Harihari and Karangarua soils where hump & hollowing is required. While coastal sands and peats and Pakihi soils are common, most are under native forest. Any cleared area will require some drainage if it is to be farmed.

2.2. FACTORS TO CONSIDER WHEN CHOOSING DRAINAGE METHOD

Cost

It is more costly to flip humus iron podzols and gley soils developed from stony subsoils (either glacial or alluvial) that have a pan above cemented gravel or boulders.

Texture

It is not ideal to flip podzols with a high content of silt or clay on flat land (Figure 5). Without the slope to aid lateral drainage, the fine silt and clays reconsolidate, causing a rapid decline in water infiltration.

Debris

The amount of debris needs to be considered. In some situations more finishing work (Chapter 6.3) may be required to deal with wood, stones and boulders brought up to the surface.

Soil and land variability

A paddock may have hollows of peat, or ridges of stones dispersed amongst sandy, silty and stony materials. To decide how and where to place drains so the water escapes, spend some time with an experienced operator.

Figure 5. Silty soils may be better suited to hump & hollowing than flipping (photo courtesy of Craig Ross, Landcare Research Ltd).

Look for visual clues, such as exposed profiles. Dig representative test holes and complete a development plan (Chapter 4.3). This will minimise the risk of developing the wrong areas of the farm and is an important starting point for the operator to help identify costs and suitability of methods. Depending on variability, the operator may need to adjust development methods as they go.

Table 2. Summary of soil profile factors to consider when planning development to improve drainage.

Soil type	Depth to gravels, type of parent material	Soil texture	Peat
Recent, Brown, Podzol	Alluvial, glacial	Sand, silt, clay	Shallow, deep
Recent soils may only need drains in hollows or development in problem areas.	Depth to gravel is a key determinant of cost. Cemented glacial gravels require more mechanical effort than looser alluvial gravels so are more expensive to develop.	Heavy soils aren't suitable for flipping without contouring as they reconsolidate. Mixing gravels with finer texture material may improve infiltration and increase water holding capacity.	If peat is shallow then it can be flipped and mixed with stony subsoil. Deep peats will be costly to flip or hump & hollow.
Podzols (Pakihi) soils require some flipping to break pans and minimise weep lines.			

FURTHER INFORMATION

Landcare Research Ltd S-maps provide the most up to date data on soil types, however, many areas on the West Coast have not been included yet: <http://smap.landcareresearch.co.nz>

Farmers reference booklet 'Soils of the West Coast', Meat and Wool New Zealand: <http://maxa.maf.govt.nz/sff/about-projects/search/06-144/soils-of-the-west-coast.pdf>

The best general reference remains 'Soil Bureau Bulletin 27 – General Survey of the soils of the South Island, New Zealand', DSIR 1968. Maps 1, 3, 5, 7, 8 relate to Buller/Westland.

More specific data is given in the old Ministry of Works & Development, Land Resource Inventory Worksheets. These are normally used in conjunction with Bulletin 27 or local maps such as the NZ Soil Survey Report 17 'Soils of the Inangahua Depression, South Island, NZ' to give the soil types.

CHAPTER 3. BENEFITS OF IMPROVING DRAINAGE

3.1. FARMER OBSERVATIONS

Based on farmer experience benefits of development include:

- Increased carrying capacity:
 - shallow drainage and pasture development increase carrying capacity from <1 cow/ha to 1.5 cows/ha.
 - flipping and new pasture increase carrying capacity from 1–1.5 cows/ha to 2.5–3 cows/ha.
- Ability to maintain the farm stocking rate on a smaller farm area. Retire the most marginal land and retain areas of native bush.
- Improved stock health. Reduced incidence of mastitis, metabolic stress related problems and lameness.
- Drier land conditions which allow for wintering of cattle, calving dates to be brought forward and cow condition to be more easily maintained.
- Cows are in milk for longer.
- More time and more area to make and utilise supplements.
- Ability to drive on the land to apply lime and fertiliser.
- Stock movement and weed control is easier to manage.
- More attractive and valuable land.

3.2. FINDINGS FROM FIELD TRIALS AND MONITORING

Field monitoring and trials add some scientific support to farmer observations and experiences.

3.2.1. Modification improves infiltration and drainage – example following flipping

On Cape Foulwind the pre-flipping average rainfall intensity of 13 mm/hour was 2–13 times greater than the soil's ability to absorb the water, resulting in ponding and/or runoff. Flipping improved infiltration and removed the constraint of poor drainage (Table 3).

Table 3. Improvements in water infiltration rate after flipping at Cape Foulwind (2001–03).

Type of development	Soil type	Years developed	Infiltration rate (mm/hour)
Undeveloped land	Sandy podzol	–	<1–8
Flipped	Humic podzol	1 year	10–23
Flipped	Sandy podzol	3 years	28–62

3.2.2. Modification increases pasture production – example following flipping

Figure 6 illustrates improvements in pasture growth over ten months on three farms. Improving drainage increased production by 9,000 kg DM/ha or 42% compared with unflipped paddocks. Milk production increased over six seasons by 58, 65 and 71% on the three farms.

Figure 6. Pasture growth rate (kg DM/ha/day) averaged across three farms from June 2002 to February 2003, Cape Foulwind.

On one farm the 3 year average dry matter production for three flipped paddocks grown under a high fertility nitrogen (N) regime and using new pasture species was in excess of 18,000 kg DM/ha.

3.2.3. Modification improves soil fertility – examples following hump & hollowing

Soil organic matter (SOM) can accumulate very rapidly after hump & hollowing (Figure 7a) and occurs with the build-up and cycling of nutrients[†]; for example, the amount of anaerobically mineralisable N, an indicator of plant-available N, increases as SOM increases (Figure 7b).

Animal excretal returns are particularly important to increase fertility. Where the animals excrete can result in differences in fertility between humps & hollows. Most of the nutrients that cows ingest are excreted.

Figure 7. Change in the amount of a) soil organic matter (soil carbon) and b) mineralisable nitrogen in the top 15 cm of soil on humps following modification. Data are from a survey of paddocks developed from similar soil material.

3.2.4. Potential pasture production increases over time

Pasture productivity is closely linked to soil development. Recently modified soils typically have lower rates of production than soils that have had time to develop under several years of continuous grazing (Figure 8).

Typically more pasture is produced on humps and upper slopes than in the hollows and lower slopes (Figure 9). This is related to greater build-up and cycling of nutrients on the upper slopes.

Figure 8. Potential dry matter (DM) production averaged across nine hump & hollowed paddocks (mean of 2 years).

[†]Ministry for Primary Industries (MPI) Sustainable Farming Fund (SFF) project 07/143: Best management practices to optimise nutrient use efficiency on modified soils of the South Island West Coast.

Despite this difference in total production, pasture response to N fertiliser (kg DM per kg of N fertiliser – the slope of the lines in Figure 9) is often similar between the humps, slopes and hollows, at least in the early stages of development¹. Both the lower and upper slopes of the humps & hollows are N deficient, limiting pasture production.

As development continues (5–10 years onwards) there is evidence that the pasture response to N fertiliser is greater on the lower slopes than on the upper slopes.

Figure 9. Annual pasture production responses (dry matter; DM) to nitrogen fertiliser from trials (cut/non-grazed) on nine paddocks at three stages of development (i.e. 1, 5 and 10 years) following hump & hollowing. Error bar is the least significant difference ($P < 0.05$).

¹Nutrient use efficiency on hump & hollows systems on the South Island's West Coast – Guidelines for improved fertiliser use and soil nutrient management. Westland Milk Products Ltd website: <http://www.westland.co.nz/>

Differences in responses are related to nutrient availability, especially N. Because of relatively more animal excretal returns and plant-soil nutrient cycling to the upper slopes, they are less N deficient than the lower slopes. Consequently the more N deficient lower slopes have larger pasture responses to fertiliser N (Figure 10). Differences in soil nutrient availability across the humps & hollows has important implications for managing fertiliser applications (Chapter 7).

Figure 10. Nutrient transfer as soils develop over time.

CHAPTER 4. PLANNING

The aim of drainage is to remove excess water from the soil to enhance plant production. Where possible the natural soil and land characteristics and features should be used to remove water quickly and effectively.

Good planning is key to a successful land development project. This will help avoid unexpected costs and will minimise maintenance and repair costs following modification. Good planning is likely to increase long-term economic returns.

Consider the following steps before starting development (refer to Appendix C for a Land Development Planning Checklist).

4.1. SEEK ADVICE

Before you start, talk to:

- Farmers who have developed their land.
- Experienced contractors who can provide useful tips.
- Farm advisors as they have probably seen land development all over the West Coast.
- West Coast Regional Council – what consents are required, what rules apply, are there any consent and compliance costs?
- Your accountant and bank manager – what are the development costs and economic returns, how much is feasible for you to develop at any one time?

Consider starting off with a smaller area as there may be false economy involved with developing a large area but cutting costs.

4.2. RESOURCE MANAGEMENT ACT

In accordance with the Regional Land and Water Plan for the West Coast, resource consents will be required. If conditions associated with the permitted activity cannot be met, please refer to the schedule of rules.

Hump & hollowing activities are associated with earthworks and discharges. The Regional Land and Water Plan 2014 refers to hump & hollowing on the West Coast as earthworks, and fertiliser applications as discharges to land. These activities are:

- Rule 1: Permitted activities on land, in areas outside erosion prone areas
- or
- Rule 13: Restricted discretionary activities on land areas within the Brunner catchment, or wetlands

- Rule 15: Discretionary activity on land (specific to Lake Brunner)
- Rule 74: Permitted discharges to land.

If one or more of the conditions associated with these rules (Appendix A) cannot be met, a resource consent is required. Failure to comply may result in an infringement or abatement notice or prosecution. Contact the West Coast Regional Council to check resource consent requirements and to determine what mitigation is necessary to comply with relevant rules.

Even if you don't need a resource consent, you must tell the Regional Council that you are planning a development before you start work (Rule 1, Condition (i) of the permitted activity rule).

Regional Council rules for hump & hollowing can be found on the West Coast Regional Council's website www.wcrc.govt.nz or in Appendix A at the back of this guide. Alternatively, call 0508 800 118 and ask to speak to a Consents Officer.

4.3. DEVELOPMENT PLAN

A ground plan of your land and the potential development site is important. Like a building design for a house, it should show all the important features and is the basis for the land shaping and drainage development. Use this plan to mark on important features (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Example of a land drainage plan based on an aerial photograph.

Additional, larger scale plans should be used to show more detailed paddock features such as drains, gateways and troughs.

4.4. AERIAL PHOTOGRAPHS AND MAPS

Aerial photographs and topographical maps help identify natural drainage and contours of large blocks (Figure 12). Scaled maps will help to estimate fence lengths to improve budget calculations. Maps may be available from the Regional Council or from websites such as:

- <http://www.linz.govt.nz/land/maps/linz-topographic-maps/map-chooser>
- www.tumonz.co.nz
- www.openstreetmap.org
- www.earth.google.com

Figure 12. Aerial photos allow for identification of land features to assist with planning.

4.5. DRAINAGE

Understanding the existing drainage system is crucial.

- Where is the natural drainage? Utilise existing drains and contours as much as possible.
- Where do streams and gullies run?
- Where does the water currently drain off the farm?
- Will you need new culverts or drains?

Drainage terminology:

Pilot, field or trench drains refer to surface or subsurface drains within the paddock e.g. the pilot drains at the bottom of a hollow. Main drains are large drains that collect water from several paddocks or the farm, while intermediate collector drains are those that the field drains connect to; these may also be main drains.

Mark these drainage features on your farm plan. Improving land drainage will increase the peak stream flows and may require enlarging drains. Culverts may be required under races.

4.6. PADDOCK SIZE AND FENCE CLEARING

- What is the total area you are developing?
- How many paddocks do you want to subdivide the area into?
- What size and shape are practical? Consider the drainage features and farm management.

Draw these paddock boundaries on your farm plan.

- Identify existing fences (these will need to be removed). Fencing wire wrapped around the excavator's tracks will delay progress.

4.7. STOCK ACCESS AND WATER TROUGHS

- Will new races be required and if so where would they be best located?
- Think about where water troughs need to be (stock often camp around gateways and troughs so to avoid pugging it may be a good idea to site them away from gateways).

Two troughs per paddock will make break feeding easier and increase the water availability to stock. It is also better to have at least two gates per paddock for efficient stock access and pasture management.

Stock access on to humps & hollows will vary depending on the design and firmness of the completed surface. Discuss these factors with your contractor and draw on the experiences of other farmers. Where possible, have your gateways marked so the contractor can plan the humps (position gateways so they open on to the hump crown).

Consider drawing these races, troughs and gateways on paddock scale plans.

4.8. EFFLUENT MANAGEMENT

- If a new farm effluent disposal system is required, plan for excavation and construction of ponds.
- Check with the Regional Council whether resource consents are required, or if it complies as a permitted activity.
- Effluent is an important source of nutrients and should be considered a key component of farm feed and nutrient management.
- Identify areas that may be used for storage and effluent disposal.
- Ensure you have planned to provide a large enough area for effluent disposal.
- Ensure effluent cannot enter water bodies, drains and troughs.

- Decide/mark on a plan where subsurface pipes and hydrants will be located.
- Discuss with farm consultants and other experts.
- Important resources:
 - A guide to managing farm dairy effluent – West Coast.
<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/publications/environment/a-guide-to-managing-farm-dairy-effluent-west-coast/>
 - Dairy effluent compliance checklist – West Coast.
<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/publications/environment/effluent-compliance-checklist-west-coast/>

4.9. SEDIMENT CONTROL

Soil disturbance during land development can result in sediment loss (Figure 13). Sediment should not be allowed to run off into natural waterways; use silt or sediment traps and additional sediment control measures, e.g. hay bale fences.

Maintain riparian strips along the banks of creeks to reduce soil and nutrient runoff and to minimise erosion where main drains feed into creeks. Stabilise banks as quickly as possible.

Mark the location of proposed riparian margins and sediment traps on your farm plan.

Figure 13. Excessive silt runoff following development.

4.10. VEGETATION

- Vegetation clearing can add dramatically to the cost of development, i.e. regrowth bracken, manuka, gorse, broom (associated with cut down native or exotic forest), semi reverted old pasture with declining drainage or rush regrowth.
- Vegetation amount and density will dictate whether it is removed, surface incorporated or buried. Large material must be removed, smaller litter may be buried by flipping and trenching.
- Excessive burying of trash can cause slumping over time.

- If there is gorse or manuka scrub present it is best to spray this up to 6 months before work commences. This will help the contractor, especially if it has been crushed (and perhaps burnt) and limits regrowth after cultivation.
- If there are stands of bush or trees that may add to the aesthetics of the farm and provide other functions, consider leaving them undeveloped (Chapter 8).

4.11. EFFECT OF LAND DEVELOPMENT ON THE FARM SYSTEM

Think about the effect of land development on the whole farm system. Loss of pasture due to land development may create a short-term feed shortage. How will this be managed?

One of the flow-on effects of pasture development is that with improved drainage there is a need to carry a higher stocking rate to utilise the extra feed. This can create issues in the future:

- Can the farm infrastructure meet the increased cow numbers?
- Will you need a bigger shed and/or tractor?
- How will it affect the number of staff required?

4.12. CONSULTATION

Inform neighbours about your development plans and consider how they may be affected, e.g. sediment in waterways, changing water catchment patterns, increased noise from machinery or landscape aesthetics.

4.13. ONGOING COSTS AND BUDGETING

There are significant ongoing costs following development. You may face new costs from increased fertiliser, particularly N, in the first 3 years. You may also need follow-up lime and increased spot spraying of weeds such as gorse after development (Figure 14). Ongoing maintenance inputs will also be higher due to increased production.

Figure 14. Routine spot spraying for weeds such as gorse may be required, flipped Pakihi soil, Westport.

CHAPTER 5. CHANGES IN LAND DEVELOPMENT METHODS

Development methods have evolved to overcome low productivity in wet hollows, prevent weep lines on slopes and improve soil water holding capacity on sandy sites.

5.1. PRODUCTIVITY OF HOLLOWES

Unproductive hollows have been a problem in many hump & hollow developments, largely where they remain wet (Figure 15). Flipping the lower slopes and hollows can increase productivity. Drier hollows mean they can also be driven on.

Figure 15. Unproductive hollows, Arnold Valley.

5.2. SEEPAGE AND WEEP LINES

Seepage occurs where drainage meets the old ground surface (which is now the mid or lower slope, Figure 16). If the water cannot drain downwards it will surface, causing weep lines (Figure 17).

Figure 16. Water seeping out mid slope at the point of the old soil surface, Kapitea Creek.

Figure 17. Weep lines (in red) occurring at and below the original ground surface.

Rushes growing from the weep line down into the hollow are symptomatic of poor drainage (Figure 18). Flipping the lower slopes and hollows enables the water to drain and flow to the bottom of the hollow. This is becoming more important now that new humps & hollows are much wider than the original ones.

Figure 18. Rushes indicate inadequate drainage on slopes, Buller Gorge.

5.3. DROUGHT MANAGEMENT

In recent years development practices have evolved to avoid soils being over drained, causing water stress (Figure 19). Where possible on sandy or overly stony sites, contractors will mix subsoil and organic soil material to improve soil water retention.

Figure 19. Water-stressed pasture post-development.

CHAPTER 6. UNDERTAKING LAND DEVELOPMENT

6.1. FLIPPING

Follow the checklist in Chapter 4 and Appendix C. Check you understand the natural drainage. Where is the drainage water likely to seep away to? This is likely to be at some point down gradient of the development. It is pointless developing one area and having the water move directly into another productive area, causing excessive waterlogging. Therefore, it may be necessary to increase the size of drains further down the property to carry this water away. Consider doing this in the year before you start the development.

6.1.1. Excavation

When flipping land, excavators remove the topsoil, put it to the side and then dig to the depth required to break up the top iron pans (approximately 1–4 m depending on the soil texture and the number of pans, Figure 20). The aim is to move the water table at least 1 m down the profile providing good aeration for root growth. On sandy soils 1 m may be adequate where the main impeding pan is near the surface. A greater depth may be required if multiple pans exist or there is a lot of organic matter in the topsoil. Depth to iron pans, their permeability, organic matter content and gravel material will vary across the site.

Be prepared to adjust flipping depth across the site.

Once operators have sufficient working space in front of the excavator they will mix the subsoil gravels with topsoil, filling in as they go. Larger vegetation is deeply buried but vegetation such as bracken may be incorporated through all layers. The process is slow and, depending on the size of the excavator (from 7 to 40 t), it can take 20–50 hours per ha.

Iron pans vary in strength and can be difficult to penetrate. On sandy soils where thick cemented layers are present down the profile, ripping the site or using an impact point to shatter pans may be beneficial before using the bucket for mixing. Physical constraints such as boulders in the subsoil will limit the depth the excavator can reach.

Figure 20. Excavation stage of flipping, Cape Foulwind.

Consider the contour of the land when deciding how deep to excavate. To avoid weepelines on sloping terrain deeper excavation will encourage vertical drainage. Silty gley soils or peats in inter-dunal areas have poor drainage so these areas should be hump & hollowed (i.e. lateral drainage should be utilised) rather than the whole site being flipped. If these areas are small or too deep they may best be set aside as fenced off wetlands.

An option for silty soils overlying gravels (which may be expensive to flip) is to dig large trenches about every 12 m. The inter-trench boggy material is mixed with the original material removed from the trench; breaking of the iron pans and disturbing the material improves the drainage. While this improves both vertical and lateral drainage it is not as successful as flipping.

Where there are slight depressions or drainage channels the area can be completely flipped and then the natural channels reinstated and contoured. Riparian vegetation needs to be left along natural waterways.

6.1.2. Levelling

A range of methods can be used to level:

- Using a bulldozer to roughly level the land and/or create contour. This could take anywhere between 1.5 and 5 hours per ha. At this stage the soil will be very wet and loose. It is important for the bulldozer to be moving forward, as constant backward-forward motions cause variable consolidation and difficulty in creating the contour. Depending on ground conditions, it may be possible to use a grader for levelling.
- Using a levelling bar on the excavator. This enables some shaping to be done immediately, saving later bulldozer costs. A quick clip enables the operator to rapidly interchange between the levelling bar and the bucket.
- Using a large tractor, e.g. 150 HP 4WD with a big leveller instead of a bulldozer (a lower cost option). This tends to leave a less even surface and narrow lines of surface stones. Discing may also be carried out at this stage to coarsely level and hasten drying.

Once the soil has dried a little and slightly consolidated, use a tractor with a levelling bar and coarse harrows or a heavy duty maxitil with a rotary crumbler to create a rough bed. Surface working, such as grubbing, can then take place to get a suitable seedbed. Grubbing may loosen and lift wood that was previously buried. Remove excess wood that has been brought to the surface.

Figure 21. Young cows grazing after land development by flipping, Cape Foulwind.

Aim to complete development within one season. Where time is less important (such as when developing previously unfarmed land), a 6 month delay prior to the last workings and sowing can allow the land to naturally settle, reducing slumping effects later.

6.2. HUMP & HOLLOWING

6.2.1. Installing drains

Spacing of drains is key to the success of the development. In traditional agricultural drainage systems, field drains are evenly spaced and feed into collector or main drains. Spacing is determined by factors including the soil's drainage characteristics. Essentially the hollows or pilot drains and trench drains act as field drains and will need to feed into a collector drain from each paddock. If drains are too far apart you will end up with wet areas.

Typically in hump & hollow systems the main drainage system was dug first; the bottom of the collector drain about 1 m below the bottom of the hollow (Figure 22). These drains dictated the direction of the hump & hollows, the maximum depth of the hollow and the height of the hump.

Pilot drains carry the runoff from the hump to the collector drain (Figure 23). As a guide there should be a fall of at least 300 mm from the pilot drain to the collector drain. A 200 mm rise from the bottom of the pilot drain to the start of the contour of the hump is recommended. This is increased to 300 mm for Pakihi and peat ground as more runoff is expected. Where hollows are flipped these dimensions are less applicable.

Where the land is contoured, pilot drains may not be evenly spaced as development works with the natural contours. These will still feed the collector or main drain.

Figure 22. A collector drain servicing a hump & hollowed paddock.

Figure 23. Pilot drains leading to a collector drain on hump & hollowed Brown soils, Maimai Valley.

6.2.2. Trench drains

Additional “trench” drains may be dug mid slope (see 6.2.5). Typically these are flipped. Some gravel from the flipped subsoil is normally retained on the surface of the humps. The trenches not only provide access to the gravel but unwanted material from the surface can be buried in the trench. Generally these trenches are shallow and wide to provide a large volume of stones for mixing with the soil. In most cases, to remove drainage water, it is necessary to connect the trenches to a collector or main drain.

6.2.3. Sediment traps and drain clearing

It is important to construct sediment traps (relatively wide, short and deep excavations in the main drainage channels) to catch coarse suspended material runoff following development. Consult Regional Council experts to determine the design and location of in-channel traps and refer to the ‘Sustainable drainage management’^{††} document.

As a rule of thumb the trap should be 1.5 times wider than the drain with a length from 4–10 times the width; about 1.5 m deeper than the average bed level. For example, for a 2 m wide channel, 0.5 m deep, the traps should be 3 m wide and at least 8 m long with a depth of at least 2 m.

Fine suspended sediment that does not settle out can be removed using filters downstream. Filters can be made of cloth or hay bales. If discharges still contain suspended particles the final discharge could be channeled through a wetland – i.e. a slow meandering waterway with riparian vegetation (either natural or constructed, Chapter 8).

All sediment traps will fill with sediment and require regular checking and emptying. Drains will require regular maintenance to remove sediment and weed.

Sediment traps should be fenced as they are a potential hazard.

6.2.4. Humps

The gradient of the slope of the hump depends on the type of soil you are contouring (Figure 24).

Most contractors and farmers agree on the following principles.

Recent soils (e.g. river flats)

- As these soils contain gravel and sands they are generally quite free draining and don’t require a steep gradient. In some cases they may not benefit from any modification as this may result in them drying out too quickly. An approach is to flip only the problem areas.

Figure 24. Hump development working with existing contours.

- Where drainage requires hump & hollowing, the height of the hump is usually around 1 m above and the hollow 1 m below the original ground level giving a total height of 2 m from bottom of hollow to top of hump, over a 30–40 m wide hump (Figure 25).

Podzols (e.g. Pakihi) soils

- In Pakihi land, iron pans are usually close to the surface. The bottom of the pilot drain should be below this depth, providing better drainage which results in a drier base for farm vehicles.
- Often the slope on these humps is steeper as the ground is poorly draining, i.e. the height of the hump is usually around 1.5 m above and the hollow 1.5 m below the original ground level giving a total height of 3 m from bottom of hollow to top of hump for a 30–40 m wide hump (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Hump & hollowing without trenching or flipping of lower slopes and hollows (Recent and Podzol soils).

Peat

- Peats shrink considerably when drained. Unless the peats are shallow and there is sufficient sandy material or gravels to mix with the peat (and/or good slopes for runoff and consolidation to occur), then draining peats may have limited benefits. Be prepared for reduced grazing during wetter periods due to wet ground.
- Where gravels can be accessed these can be bought up by flipping to be mixed and contoured with the peaty material. Where possible the slopes at the original ground level should be flipped and mixed (undercutting below the old surface).
- Where hump & hollows are constructed without flipping, the height of the hump is usually around 1.5–2 m above and the hollow 1.5–2 m below the original ground level giving a total height of 3–4 m from bottom of hollow to top of hump, over a 30–40 m wide hump. However, the depth of the hollow depends on the depth to gravels. Pilot drains need to be deeper, up to 1 m for 30 m humps or 0.5 m for 20 m humps

¹NZWERF Sustainable drainage management – Best management practice:
http://www.wet.org.nz/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/COARSE_SED_TRAP.pdf

(Figure 26). It is recommended that an open ditch is maintained in the hollow to keep the hollow dry. An open ditch is also easier to clean and maintain.

- Installing culverts through hollows will help keep stock out of the pilot drains.

Figure 26. Hump & hollowing without trenching or flipping of lower slopes and hollows (peat).

6.2.5. Recent advances in hump & hollowing

There has been a move to improve the drainage on humps & hollows by digging trenches on the slopes and flipping the lower slopes and hollows (Chapter 5). Trenches act as drains, provide a source of gravels and a place to dispose of unwanted material. They also enable wider and flatter humps and hollows, e.g. Figure 27. On sloping land, contouring may be more appropriate (Figure 28).

Figure 27. Larger contoured hump & hollows are now more common, Inangahua.

If the soil is predominantly fine material (i.e. silt and clay) this can be mixed with the gravels to increase water retention during dry periods. Gravels and sandy material are unable to hold much water. A rule of thumb is to try and get a 50:50 ratio mix of gravels with finer textured soil material. Soils are flipped further down the slope and in the hollows (Figure 29).

Figure 28. Contour flipping before (right) and after (left).

Figure 29. Hump & hollowing incorporating trenches and flipping. Trenches should connect to a downstream drain.

6.2.6. Machinery

The two most commonly used pieces of equipment are excavators and bulldozers. Excavator boom length generally dictates the width of the hump. Approaches include:

- An excavator and bulldozer; the excavator roughly forms the humps while the bulldozer develops the contours. This approach helps consolidate the hump, reducing it by about 500 mm, allowing wheel tractor access sooner.
- A single excavator with a levelling bar to level and do the initial contouring.
- Although basic hump & hollowing is often done with a 20 t excavator, bigger machinery (30–40 t) may be required if digging trenches in slopes and flipping hollows, especially in the harder glacial gravels.

Where the hollows are flipped, the teeth on the bucket may last anywhere from 2 weeks in the harder glacial gravels to 4+ weeks in alluvial gravels.

6.2.7. Avoiding slumping

Stumps should be removed or at least buried in the middle of the humps. Failure to do so will result in their reappearance once the ground has settled adding to maintenance costs. Some material can be buried in trenches.

Burying too much vegetation will result in localised subsidence or slumping and long-term ponding issues. Slumping can occur soon after development. Old stumps could take more than 5 years to break down. These areas will require some touch up work to recontour (a good time to do this is when regrassing).

6.2.8. Preparation for sowing

If the paddock is left for 2 or 3 months to dry and consolidate, spray with an herbicide (e.g. glyphosate), then disc lengthways along the humps. After this use the harrows at least twice to give an even surface. Using the harrows on the diagonal helps to cover

wheel tracks and prevent ridging. With any levelling be careful not to drag too much soil into the hollows. Heavy rolling will further consolidate the ground in preparation for sowing (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Heavy rolled and consolidated seedbed.

6.3. FINISHING WORK

Debris (i.e. wood and boulders), will be left on the surface after development work. When hump & hollowing involves trenching and flipping more debris will be brought up.

Although there is a cost to removing this material there are a number of advantages to providing an even surface. The benefits include: easier light cultivation (e.g. discing), better silage making conditions and improved fertiliser spreading (it will also be much more comfortable to drive across the paddocks).

6.4. SEEDBED PREPARATION AND PASTURE SOWING

Cultivation for seedbed preparation will depend on what has been done previously during the levelling phase. This can be minimal for sandy soils.

Sowing options include:

- An air seeder or similar drill followed by rolling with a Cambridge roller (Figure 31).
- Roller drill.
- Broadcast, followed by harrows in front of a roller to incorporate seed.

Consolidation of the seedbed can be delayed to ensure new seedlings can quickly penetrate the topsoil. An option is to heavy roll once grass is well established (i.e. 10–15 cm high).

Figure 31. Newly established seedbed where rolling occurred before drilling.

CHAPTER 7. MANAGEMENT

7.1. FERTILISER AND LIME – PRE-PLANT (FLIPPING AND HUMP & HOLLOWING)

Flipping and hump & hollowing will invert large volumes of infertile, acidic subsoil requiring large inputs of lime and fertiliser to address nutrient deficiencies.

The amount of fertiliser and lime to apply should be based on soil nutrient analysis. Sample to 150 mm when carrying out final levelling work. Ensure that the samples are representative of the block and are analysed in good time so that lime can be applied before surface working.

A standard soil test includes pH, Olsen P, Calcium (Ca), Potassium (K), Magnesium (Mg) and Sodium plus Sulphate Sulphur (SO₄-S).

Other tests worth considering are organic matter or total carbon and total N and Boron (B). Discuss with your fertiliser representative or consultant.

Basal lime should be worked in during seedbed preparation. As a guide 700–1,000 kg/ha will lift pH by 0.1 in the top 75 mm or 150 mm in very stony soil. Aim to lift pH to 5.8–6.2. Generally 3–5 t/ha of lime will be required to achieve the desired total pH increase. Where more than 5 t/ha is required, the balance can be applied 6–12 months later. Some lime can be applied as dolomite where Mg is also required.

Pakihi soils are generally low in P, K, Mg and S. Recent and Brown soils lack P and S, but may have adequate Mg for grass growth. Stock should be supplemented with Mg in spring to meet animal health requirements. Brown soils may require K, but Recent soils often have sufficient K.

Prior to drilling apply capital P and S fertiliser to the surface or lightly work in. Normally 50–70 kg P/ha is required to lift Olsen P values by 10 units in the topsoil. This can be met by applying 650–900 kg/ha of Pakihi Starter Mix (0–7.5–4–14 + TE) or another Superphosphate product. Actual rates should be based on soil test results.

Hump & hollowing generally requires less development fertiliser compared to flipping. Pakihi soils should receive a significant portion of their S as elemental S to minimise significant losses via leaching.

Depending on the amounts and timing of the capital fertiliser application, additional P may be required at sowing e.g. Pakihi Starter Mix or Superphosphate. Apply N based on soil test results to help establish pasture.

7.2. ONGOING FERTILISER REQUIREMENTS AS SOILS DEVELOP

In Chapter 3 we described how soil fertility develops over time, how this is regulated by nutrient inputs and how in hump & hollow systems this leads to differences in pasture production across slopes. Hence, fertiliser requirements will similarly vary over time and across the humps & hollows (Table 4)[†].

Table 4. Summary of changes in soil organic matter, nutrient cycles and fertiliser requirements as modified soils develop.

Stage	Years	Soil organic matter	Nutrient cycling and fertiliser requirements
Early	1–3	Soil organic matter is low but increasing.	High requirements of capital fertiliser to overcome net immobilisation and nutrient deficiencies.
		High C:N ~20	Potential pasture production for the region is not yet achievable.
Developing	3–10	Soil organic matter is low to moderate but increasing rapidly.	Immobilisation is still high, but more nutrients are being released and cycled through soil and plants.
		Moderate C:N ratio ~14–18	Relatively high rates of fertiliser are still needed. Potential pasture production for the region is not yet achievable.
Late development	10+	Soil organic matter is high and further increases are slow.	Rates of immobilisation and mineralisation are similar.
		Low C:N ratio ~10–14	Lower amounts of fertiliser are required. Potential pasture production is achievable.

7.2.1. Soil and plant testing

Frequent soil and herbage testing (e.g. annually) is very important as soils develop.

Monitoring trends of plant and soil nutrient changes is important in developing soils to ensure that (i) fertiliser applications and consequent soil nutrient concentrations are within targets for pasture production and (ii) nutrient amounts are not increasing to concentrations high enough to result in environmental losses – especially P.

[†]Nutrient use efficiency on hump & hollows systems on the South Island's West Coast – Guidelines for improved fertiliser use and soil nutrient management. Westland Milk Products Ltd website: <http://www.westland.co.nz/>

On hump & hollowed soil we recommend separate samples are taken from both the upper and lower slopes so that nutrient excesses and deficiencies across the paddock can be managed.

7.2.2. Nutrient budgeting

Maintaining nutrient budgets is important to ensure that (i) nutrients removed from the soil are replaced and (ii) the nutrients are not being lost to contaminate surface and ground water, resulting in adverse environmental impacts.

The best available tool for this is OVERSEER®. However, OVERSEER® has so far not been calibrated for developing hump & hollow soils. This means it is very important to test soils and plants to ensure that nutrients stay within the target ranges.

7.3. GENERAL GUIDELINES FOR APPLYING NITROGEN AND OTHER NUTRIENTS

In early developing soils, pasture production is strongly affected by N application rates, with responses proportional to increasing application rates (e.g. up to 480 kg N/ha/year, Table 5).

Table 5. Fertiliser recommendations for the first 2–3 years following hump & hollowing.

Fertiliser application rates kg/ha/year				
N	P	S	Mg	K
240–480	56	125 ¹	100	100–150

¹30 kg as elemental S/ha

Reference: Morton & Roberts (2006)

Nitrogen requirements are likely to be closer to 250–350 kg N/ha in the second and third year. As a general guide, requirements on Brown and Recent soils are less than for Pakihi and generally less for hump & hollowing than for flipping.

As soil fertility improves (e.g. from 3-plus years), the pasture responses to high N application rates reduce. The systems are still N limited so will respond strongly to N fertiliser. Other nutrients should be applied at maintenance rates and adjusted via soil test trends.

In the older modified soils (e.g. 10-plus years), N fertiliser requirements are much lower (200–300 kg N/ha/year). Beyond these rates the pasture response to N fertiliser reduces.

On narrower hump & hollow systems where the more N deficient lower slopes have larger pasture responses to fertiliser N (Chapter 3.2.4), there may be opportunities to

target different fertiliser N application rates to the upper and the lower slopes, e.g. by applying one-third to the upper slope and two-thirds to the lower slope.

Nitrogen fertiliser should be applied little and often (e.g. 25 to 40 kg N/ha) to minimise runoff and leaching losses.

Apply K at 100–150 kg K/ha/year to ensure adequate clover K concentrations are maintained.

Soluble forms of P (e.g. superphosphate) can be substituted with slowly soluble Reactive Phosphate Rock (RPR) once target Olsen P concentrations are reached and maintenance rates are required.

Two years after hump & hollowing, Mg levels can be reduced from 80 kg Mg/ha to 40 kg Mg/ha/year to optimise herbage Mg levels (Craighead 2002).

7.4. TIMING

Fertiliser N will not be effective when it is too cold, too dry or too wet.

Greatest pasture responses to fertiliser N typically occur in spring (applied late winter and early spring).

Apply urea before (light) rainfall but avoid applications when large rainfall is forecast (>50 mm within 4 days of application). Large volatilisation losses of ammonia may occur when urea is applied to warm moist soils. Losses are minimised when urea is washed into the surface soil by about 10 mm of rain, or if using a product with a urease inhibitor.

Potassium applications should be split up to 4 times per year in the early development stage, and 2–3 times following early development.

7.5. EFFLUENT APPLICATIONS

Effluent is an important nutrient source (especially N and K). Follow Guidelines on DairyNZ's website[†].

Introduce slowly in the first year, e.g. only 1–2 times with extended breaks between applications.

[†]A guide to managing farm dairy effluent - West Coast:

<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/publications/environment/a-guide-to-managing-farm-dairy-effluent-west-coast/>

[†]Dairy effluent compliance checklist – West Coast:

<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/publications/environment/effluent-compliance-checklist-west-coast/>

7.6. MINIMISING ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS FROM FERTILISER AND EFFLUENT APPLICATION

Losses of N and P occur from intensive dairy systems and can contaminate surface and groundwater. These losses can be minimised by applying fertiliser and effluent at the appropriate amount and time, taking care when applying in the proximity of water courses.

- Apply N in small amounts (25–40 kg N/ha).
- Apply maintenance fertiliser P in a less soluble form with Reactive Phosphate Rock (RPR) and maintain soil Quick Test Olsen P levels at no higher than 30–35. There is greater potential for P loss as the amount of plant-available P increases.

Typically, greatest losses of nutrients in pastoral systems occur from animal excreta. Urine patches have very high N content and dung patches contain P. Stocking rate is a major factor in the scale of these losses, with higher stocking rates leading to higher potential nutrient losses.

- Avoid compacting soils; P is especially at risk.
- Avoid applying fertiliser to surface water bodies.
- Keep stock from waterways by using fencing, bridges and culverts.
- Use low rate effluent application systems.

7.7. FERTILISER SPREADING ON HUMPS & HOLLOWES

Delivering fertiliser to the right place at the right time is important to ensure nutrients are used efficiently.

As described in Chapter 3, responses to fertiliser can be affected by slope and position on humps & hollows; i.e. greater responses to fertiliser N placed on the lower slopes than on the upper slopes. Where this is the case, more pasture can be produced if relatively more N fertiliser is targeted to the less fertile lower slopes in the paddock.

To complicate matters, fertiliser spreading on humps & hollows is affected by the topography and is not the same as spreading on the flat.

- Applying from the top of the hump increases the total spread width (Figure 32).
- When driving on slopes, upslope and downslope patterns are not symmetrical. The magnitude of these differences will be affected by the steepness of the slopes (Figure 33).
- Applying from the hollow decreases the total spread width (Figure 34).
- Patterns differ among products (i.e. fertiliser particle size and density) and spreader types.

Figure 32. Example of the distribution pattern when fertiliser is spread from the top of a hump.

From top of hump

Symmetrical spreading pattern.

Relatively wide distribution.

Figure 33. Example of the distribution pattern when fertiliser is spread from the slope.

On slope

Asymmetrical spreading pattern – narrow upslope and wider downslope.

Fertiliser may be thrown over the other side of the hump or across to the opposite slope.

Figure 34. Example of the distribution pattern when fertiliser is spread from the hollow.

From the hollow

Symmetrical spreading pattern.

Relatively narrow distribution, as fertiliser is intercepted by the rising slope.

Figure 35 illustrates spreading patterns on the flat for bout widths (the distance between successive passes of fertiliser spreaders) that are too close, optimum and too wide. If too close, fertiliser is over-applied, but if too far apart it is under-applied.

For example, if the machine is set up to apply fertiliser evenly at a bout width of 15 m and you drive at a width of 10 m, you will apply 150% of the intended rate, whereas driving at 20 m widths will result in 75% of the intended rate being applied.

- Uniformity is also greatly affected by the accuracy of driving.
- Bout widths set up for optimum patterns differ among spreaders and products.
- The distance between humps often won't coincide with these optimum widths.

Guidelines for fertiliser recommendations on modified soils can be found on the Westland Milk Products Ltd website[†].

Figure 35. Fertiliser spreading patterns and overlap on flat ground.

7.8. MACHINERY SAFETY

Special care needs to be taken with driving machinery over modified ground:

- Sloping ground needs to be managed differently from flat land when operating machinery (fertiliser spreading, etc.). Make staff aware of the dangers, particularly if they are not used to traversing undulating ground.
- Slumping can occur on hump & hollow and flipped land. Take extra care for the first 12 months on newly developed land.

[†]Nutrient use efficiency on hump & hollows systems on the South Island's West Coast – Guidelines for improved fertiliser use and soil nutrient management. Westland Milk Products Ltd website: <http://www.westland.co.nz/>

[†]A guide for fertiliser spreading on humps & hollows. Westland Milk Products Ltd website: <http://www.westland.co.nz/>

7.9. PASTURE SPECIES

A wide variety of species and cultivars are available. Obtain expert advice to decide what is best suited. Cultivars should be chosen for their persistence, quality (palatability), production and growth pattern. Due to the summer moist conditions on the West Coast, many grass and clover species will grow well.

Perennial ryegrass pastures grown in good fertility conditions and managed well have good persistence. Choices include true perennial and long rotation cultivars and more palatable tetraploid and high sugar grasses; each has its pros and cons.

Perennial ryegrass cultivars with new endophytes such as AR1, AR37, NEA2 are resistant, in most situations, to pests such as Argentine stem weevil which can be problematic in some seasons.

Annual grasses may be grown if weed (gorse) issues and slumping is expected. Further spraying, levelling and resowing should be anticipated. Annual grasses also suit if establishment is delayed in winter.

It is not recommended that brassica crops are grown in the first year of development due to specific nutrient requirements, weed issues and pugging considerations.

Fescues are an option for summer dry conditions (particularly on sandy soils and runoff blocks) and when mixed with clover can produce highly nutritious pastures but require careful grazing management.

White clover species with large leaves (e.g. Kopu II) generally suit more open dairy pastures, while small to medium leaved clovers with higher stolon density (e.g. Huia) persist longer.

Deep rooting herbs such as chicory or plantain are also beneficial for moisture tolerance and trace element nutrition for stock. Some farmers delay their introduction 6–12 months until post-sowing weed control is complete, where they are direct drilled into the existing pasture with a reduced rate of ryegrass and clover.

Recommended sowing rates for ryegrass and clover mixes for dairying after development are:

- 18–28 kg/ha of ryegrass (most preferably as perennial types), and
- 3–5 kg/ha of mixed white clovers, preferably with 1 kg/ha of herbs.

Higher sowing rates are required when broadcasting than when drilling. Inoculated clover seed should be used.

7.10. WHEN TO SOW

Sow pasture in late summer to early autumn and graze lightly once before winter to promote good spring growth. Weed competition will tend to be higher with spring sowing, increasing spray costs.

Air seeders or roller drills are often used although the latter is not very effective in stony ground. Fine seed beds are prone to drying and wind erosion, so roller drills and broadcasting can be risky in warm dry conditions.

On very sandy soils, pea and oat crops can be mulched in to the soil to enhance the water holding capacity of the seed bed before establishing new pasture.

7.11. POST-SOWING MANAGEMENT

Weed control is important in the first spring. It is best to spray when weeds are seedlings.

Choose chemicals to control the weed species likely to be present. Base this on previous experience or seek expert advice. Chemicals such as 2,4DB and MCPB are often the most cost effective. 2,4DB will give better control of willow weed, pepper weed, docks and ragwort, but will damage red clover and herbs. Glyphosate products can be used for spot spraying.

7.12. GRAZING

Before the first grazing, usually 6–10 weeks after sowing, check that the plants are firmly anchored using the 'pull test'.

Graze lightly when pasture is 100–125 mm high leaving 40–60 mm of cover.

It will be easier to pull plants in soils with high organic matter (peat) content. Some farmers choose to delay final rolling until the seedling stage and graze after plant recovery to encourage early deep rooting. On both stony and clay soils it is not advisable to delay rolling as the soil gets too hard and stones can't be adequately pushed below the surface, making it difficult to use the paddock for hay/silage production.

Graze new pasture with young stock to reduce plant and pugging damage. Avoid grazing in wet conditions. In spring, graze more frequently to encourage ryegrass tillering and to prevent shading of clover. Graze more lightly and less frequently in dry conditions. If the pasture turns yellow or dies back it may be N deficient (browns at the tip); graze then apply N. We recommend applying small amounts of N fertiliser after each grazing.

Where possible avoid taking hay or silage crops in the first year; if this is unavoidable, cut the crop high to leave greater residuals.

7.13. PASTURE PESTS AFTER DEVELOPMENT

Porina caterpillars and manuka beetle can cause severe and extensive damage on land developments on the West Coast.

Porina are often the first pest to invade newly developed areas. Porina moths can lay 2,000–3,000 eggs each. Severe pasture damage can result from relatively small flights of moths. Recent research[†] suggests porina moth flights and egg laying on the West Coast can occur from November until February which means timing of control measures can be very difficult. If large flights of moths are observed farmers should consider treating pastures 8–10 weeks later with Dimilin® (diflubenzuron).

Manuka beetle populations normally take longer to build up. Damage may appear 3–4 years after pastures are first established. If manuka beetles are already a problem in the locality severe damage may occur within 1–2 years of pasture establishment. Anecdotally, deeper rooting herbs and fescue/cocksfoot pastures have less manuka beetle damage.

Research on West Coast pasture pests is ongoing[†]. Information on pasture pests can be accessed on the Agpest website: <http://agpest.co.nz/>

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Morton JD and Roberts AHC 2006. Pasture responses to fertiliser on renovated West Coast Pakihi soils. *Proceedings of the New Zealand Grassland Association* 68, 331–338.

[†]Ministry for Primary Industries Sustainable Farming Fund project 401443: Pest management in land use modification on the South Island West Coast.

CHAPTER 8. ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

Fencing off riparian strips and conserving wet areas has a number of benefits: for aesthetics (Figure 36) and functionality (water quality and sediment control)[†].

There are economic and environmental cost-benefits of maintaining wetlands. Low lying, deep peaty depressions can be expensive to develop and may still remain largely unproductive after development. For example, it may cost more than \$10,000/ha to develop these areas with limited return as the drained soil may still be too wet.

Figure 36. Example of area that farmer wants to fence off for reasons of aesthetics.

Undeveloped deep peaty depressions reverted to wetlands can perform many valuable functions, including:

- Trapping sediment and filtering nutrient runoff. Slow moving water through a wetland allows suspended sediment to settle out. Dissolved nutrients are absorbed by plant roots and soil micro-organisms, removing much of the nutrient and pollutant load by the time it leaves a wetland.
- Reducing the impact of floods by absorbing water during heavy rain and releasing water gradually, so flooding is reduced.

These areas can be enhanced by planting with suitable native vegetation, e.g. flax, toetoe, cabbage trees.

Identify riparian, wetland areas or stands of trees that should be fenced off at the planning stage (Chapter 4).

Stock grazing around creeks and streams can increase sediment and nutrient losses. Aim to fence waterways to exclude stock.

Information on Westland Milk Products Ltd Farm Excellence (FarmEx) programme can be found on their website www.westland.co.nz/eng/sustainability/our-environment/

[†]For information about what to plant and effective set back fencing distances see DairyNZ's document 'Getting riparian planting right on the West Coast: Your step-by-step guide for successful riparian planting': <http://www.dairynz.co.nz/media/1569775/riparian-mgmt-west-coast.pdf>

CHAPTER 9. FINANCIAL

9.1. COSTS OF DEVELOPMENT

The following is a guide to the costs associated with developing land through to the first spring. These are based on using a contractor. Some follow-up costs are also included to show the total cost of development.

Table 6. Approximate costs of land development activities.

	Cost \$/ha		
	Hump & hollow 20–30 hr/ha	Hump & hollow with flipping 22–35 hr/ha	Flipping 30–50 hr/ha
Excavator – small \$120–130/hr, medium \$140–160/hr, large \$200/hr	2,400–3,900	4,000–7,000	4,200–8,000
Bulldozer, bar levelling and/or discing, harrow, roll for seeding at \$130/hr	500–800	600–1,000	500–600
Total land preparation (cost \$/ha)	2,900–4,700	4,600–8,000	4,700–8,600

Table 7. Approximate costs of activities post-development (in the first 1–3 years).

	Actual range Cost \$/ha	Your figures Cost \$/ha
Development costs		
Picking up wood/stones	0–150	
Soil tests – before development lime and then every 12 months as soils develop	120–140	
Lime – development, 3–5 t/ha ¹	145–245	
Lime or dolomite pre-plant, 0.75–2 t/ha ²	50–300	
Capital fertiliser @ 50–70 kg P/ha	220–310	
Planter fertiliser plus first N @ 40 kg N/ha, 20 kg P/ha and 25 kg K/ha ³	150–200	
Lime, fertiliser spreading 2–4 applications	45–100	
Seed – certified perennial ryegrass/white clover, red clover or plantain, (uncertified seed), 25–35 kg/ha ⁴	180–420 (125–150)	
Sowing cost	45–90	

	Actual range Cost \$/ha	Your figures Cost \$/ha
Second N application, @ 37 kg N/ha	50	
Third N (+K) application (spring), @ 32 kg N/ha and 15 kg K/ha)	65	
Common development costs (typical range)	1,070–2,070	
Infrastructure costs, most applicable to new land		
Fencing	250–300	
Water	250–300	
New farm tracks	0–500	
Total infrastructure cost	500–1,100	
Total development costs to first spring		
Basic hump & hollow	4,470–7,870	
Hump & hollow with flipping	6,170–11,170	
Flipping	7,295–11,770	
Follow-up costs years 1–3		
Spraying	30–50	
Follow-up levelling, up to 6 hr/ha	0–800	
Seed – low rate as top up to full replant – ryegrass/white clover + plantain ⁵	50–200	
N fertiliser @ 27–50 kg N/ha/application x 2 years ⁶	150–250	
Total follow-up cost	230–1,300	
Other potential costs		
Scrub clearing ⁷		
Consents		
Purchase of additional WMP shares at \$1.50/kg MS		
Purchase of additional cows		
Herbage analysis		

¹ Lime and fertiliser costs assume farmer spread.

² Dolomite is a good development option where lime and Mg are required (supplies 80–200 kg Mg/ha).

- ³ First N applications are based on autumn sowing and N required to get to the first spring.
- ⁴ Highest costs assume 35 kg/ha rather than 25 kg/ha and novel ryegrass endophyte ryegrass used. Uncertified seed calculations in brackets.
- ⁵ Substantial re-levelling will require additional seed costs.
- ⁶ Additional N required in the short term but keep within Rule 74 of Regional Council guidelines.
- ⁷ Scrub clearing could increase costs by up to \$2,000/ha. Flipping and any trenching with hump & hollowing generally negates the need for this.

Other fertiliser costs for additional nutrients (K and Mg in particular) will be dictated by the follow-up soil and herbage tests.

Excavation and land preparation make up the bulk of the costs of development. Total costs per hectare vary with the state of the land pre-development, the soil volume actually moved, the charge out rate of the contractor, and the infrastructure that already exists (tracks, water supply, etc). The cost to repair slumping and subsequent regrassing must also be considered. **In the long run you will get better production, and spend less, if you do the job properly in the beginning.** This requires using the most appropriate equipment and a good contractor.

Significant cost savings can be made if farmers do some work themselves particularly in spreading lime and fertiliser, new fencing and land/old fence clearing.

Although a considerable investment is required to complete development work, the cost should be compared with the purchase price and the expected returns from the developed land.

9.2. COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Within the first few years after development significantly more pasture can be produced, typically achieving 10–13,000 kg DM/ha or 700–1,000 kg MS/ha.

The benefit of drainage will depend on how productive the land was pre-development, i.e. from carrying no stock to carrying 1 cow/ha. Post-development, cow numbers could increase to 2–2.5+ cows/ha, each producing 320–380 kg MS/ha. Therefore the increased production could range from 320 kg MS/ha to 950 kg MS/ha.

Production per hectare from the developed land will increase as the soils develop.

Assuming a medium term average payout of \$6.25/kg MS and an average cost of production (farm working expenses) of \$4.75/kg MS, then the difference (\$1.50/kg MS) represents the return before tax and interest.

Table 8. Return per hectare from development.

Year(s) after development	Additional production (kg MS/ha)		Return at \$1.50/kg MS (\$/kg MS)	
	Range	Average	Range	Average
Year 1	300–700	500	450–1,050	750
Year 2	500–900	700	750–1,350	1,050
Year 3 onwards	600–1,000	800	900–1,500	1,200

Costs are indicative only. While flipping may have the highest excavation costs, the ongoing maintenance costs may be less than that required for hump & hollowing (e.g. re-shaping). Scrub cover is also less of an issue as it can be buried. The costs will also vary across the block as soil and terrain changes. Therefore a farmer is unlikely to be up for the maximum costs at each step.

Although additional cost savings due to drainage will vary with each farmer's circumstances, examples include:

- The ability to make high quality supplements on farm and a wider window to make supplements. Compare with a truck and trailer unit of baleage with transport costing upwards of \$5,000.
- Ability to top pasture to maintain quality.
- Wintering on farm. One farmer commented it cost \$30,000 to winter the dairy herd in Canterbury so any reduction in numbers wintered off farm represents significant cost savings.
- Raising replacement cows on farm.
- Each condition score on a cow that doesn't need to be regained represents 160–190 kg DM or at 12 c/kg DM = \$20–23/cow, or may represent another two weeks in milk.

CHAPTER 10. CONCLUSION

Land drainage methods on the West Coast have been evolving over the last few decades and changes in techniques are likely to continue.

If you are considering new drainage development there are some key messages:

- Plan well – carefully consider the costs, complete a realistic budget and a detailed plan.
- Seek expert advice from farmers and contractors who have successfully completed development work (learn from their successes and mistakes).
- Discuss the economics with your accountant and bank manager.
- Check with the Regional Council what legal requirements may need to be met.

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Agronomic – the management of land.

Bucket flipping – general excavation when the land is flipped and/or hollows are turned over.

Gley – soil formed under high water conditions where anoxic conditions reduce chemical compounds and lower worm and micro-organism activity.

Humus – a mixture of partly decomposed organic matter that is blended with soil mineral material by soil micro-organisms.

Impervious – water cannot pass through.

Infiltration – rate at which water can move into the soil surface.

Interdune – low lying area between the dunes usually of poorer drainage as the water has been trapped preventing runoff.

Iron pans – poorly permeable or impermeable layers formed from the accumulation of leached iron compounds and organic matter.

Lateral drainage – sideways drainage, usually when drainage meets impermeable or slowly permeable material.

Main drain – large drain, typically at edge of paddock that takes water away from pilot drains to creek or river.

Pakihi soil – a general term used to cover infertile wetland soils formed on flat and gently sloping land under high rainfall, typically on the West Coast.

Peat soil – a soil containing raw or slightly decomposed organic matter accumulated under swamp conditions.

Pilot drain – drain or depression at bottom of hollow or at base of contoured land.

Podzolisation – a soil forming process where iron and aluminium compounds are leached from the upper soil layers. These leached compounds can form subsurface pans.

Texture – proportion of sand, silt, clay in a soil.

Fine textured – soil is dominated by smallest particles, i.e. clay.

Coarse textured – soil is dominated by largest particles, i.e. sand.

Trench flipping – broader, shallow trenches dug at the mid slope of a hump to bring gravels to surface, bury surface debris, and to prevent weep lines.

APPENDIX A – WEST COAST REGIONAL COUNCIL RULES

Rule regarding humping & hollowing as a permitted activity as per the Regional Land and Water Plan May 2014 (Operative)

18.1.1 Permitted Activities on Land

Rule 1. Humping and hollowing, flipping or v-blading outside riparian margins

Humping and hollowing, flipping, or v-blading in the Non-Erosion Prone Area (less than 12° slope) outside of riparian margins, and any associated discharge of sediment are **permitted activities** if all of the following conditions are met:

- (a) (i) For humping and hollowing and flipping, the area of the activity does not exceed 5 hectares per landholding in any continuous 12 month period; and
 - (ii) For v-blading either:
 - 1. The land area for new works does not exceed 10 hectares per landholding in any 12 month period; or
 - 2. The activity is undertaken on land that has previously been v-bladed; and
- (b) The activity must not cause the visual clarity of any receiving water to decrease by more than 40%, as measured by black disc beyond 12 times the river's width or 200 metres of the activity, whichever is the lesser; and
- (c) No soil or debris is placed directly in any river or lake bed; and
- (d) There is no conspicuous deposition of sediment on the bed of any water body, or on land beyond the boundary of the subject property; and
- (e) The activity does not affect any surface water take; and
- (f) The activity is not within:
 - (i) 50 metres of the Coastal Marine Area on the open coast line; or
 - (ii) 20 metres of the Coastal Marine Area elsewhere; or
 - (iii) Any wetland identified in Schedule 1 or 2; or
 - (iv) The Lake Brunner catchment; and
- (g) When operating alongside a riverbed and there is an iron pan or hard pan layer below the surface of the land then the iron pan or hard pan is not to be disturbed or broken within a distance of 20 metres from the edge of the riverbank; and
- (h) Any culverts or cut and fill batters are designed, and constructed or installed to prevent their failure and avoid causing erosion; and

- (i) The Council is notified in writing of the location and extent of the activity, at least seven working days prior to the works commencing; and
- (j) All areas disturbed by humping and hollowing and flipping are re-vegetated as soon as practicable; and
- (k) All drainage from land subject to the activity is directed through sediment control devices or traps prior to entry to any waterway; and
- (l) Any rivers, streams, or wetlands identified in Schedule 1 or 2, that could be accessed by stock from the pasture created by the humping and hollowing, flipping or v-blading activity, shall be fenced to exclude stock access; and
- (m) The discharge does not increase the flow in the receiving waterbody to the extent that it exceeds the carrying capacity of existing infrastructure.

18.1.3 Restricted Discretionary Activities on Land

Rule 13. Humping and hollowing, flipping and v-blading

Humping and hollowing, flipping, and v-blading, outside of a wetland identified in Schedule 1 or 2 and the Lake Brunner Catchment, that cannot meet any one of the conditions of a permitted activity in Rule 1, or that occurs within a riparian margin is a **restricted discretionary activity**.

Humping and hollowing activities within these areas require resource consent.

In considering any resource consent under this Rule, the Council will restrict the exercise of its discretion to the following:

- (a) The effects of erosion, sedimentation of waterways, changes in surface runoff, and measures to avoid, remedy, or mitigate adverse effects on affected persons and infrastructure located downstream;
- (b) Effects on the stability of beds and banks of rivers and streams;
- (c) Adherence to a certified engineering plan;
- (d) Setback distances from wetlands, lakes, rivers, and the coastal marine area;
- (e) Timing of the activity;
- (f) Damage to riparian vegetation, soil, natural habitats and features, and significant sites;
- (g) Effects on surface and sub surface water levels, flows, and quality;
- (h) Erosion and sediment control methods;
- (i) Effects on the natural character of wetlands, ecological values or intrinsic values;

- (j) Measures to avoid, remedy, or mitigate adverse effects on stream morphology and substrate deposition;
- (k) Cumulative effects;
- (l) Potential damage to any cultural or heritage site/area;
- (m) The relationship of Ngāi Tahu and their culture and traditions with their ancestral lands, waters, sites, wahi tapu, and other taonga;
- (n) Monitoring provisions;
- (o) The duration of the resource consent;
- (p) Bonds and financial contributions;
- (q) Review conditions of the resource consent.

18.5.1 Permitted Discharges to Land

Rule 74. Application of fertiliser

Fertiliser: means any proprietary substance specifically manufactured for use in increasing the nutrient status of land.

Except where Rule 15 applies (specific to lake Brunner) the discharge of fertiliser into or onto land is a **permitted activity** provided that all of the following conditions are met:

- (a) There is no discernible contamination of water; and
- (b) Any drift derived from the discharge is not noxious, dangerous, offensive or objectionable beyond the target area to such an extent that it has or is likely to have an adverse effect on the environment; and

In the Lake Brunner catchment:

- (c) Phosphorus fertiliser shall not be discharged to land that is developed under Rule 15 unless it has a water solubility of less than 10%.

APPENDIX B – FURTHER INFORMATION

West Coast Regional Council:

- Review of Humping and Hollowing on the West Coast: Steph Brown, Principal Resource Management Planner, Opus International Consultants Ltd, 2004.
- Regional Land & Riverbed Management Plan: West Coast Regional Council, 2012.

Westland Milk Products Ltd:

Website: <http://www.westland.co.nz/>

- Farm Excellence Programme (FarmEx).
- A guide for fertiliser spreading on humps & hollows.
- Nutrient use efficiency on hump & hollow systems on the South Island's West Coast – Guidelines for improved fertiliser use and soil nutrient management.

DairyNZ Ltd website:

- A guide to managing farm dairy effluent – West Coast.
<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/publications/environment/a-guide-to-managing-farm-dairy-effluent-west-coast/>
- Dairy effluent compliance checklist – West Coast.
<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/publications/environment/effluent-compliance-checklist-west-coast/>
- Getting riparian planting right on the West Coast: Your step-by-step guide for successful riparian planting.
<http://www.dairynz.co.nz/media/1569775/riparian-mgmt-west-coast.pdf>

Other:

- Soils of the West Coast – Farmer reference booklet:
<http://maxa.maf.govt.nz/sff/about-projects/search/06-144/soils-of-the-west-coast.pdf>
- Sustainable drainage management- Best management practice:
http://www.wet.org.nz/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/COARSE_SED_TRAP.pdf
- Landcare Research Ltd S-maps: <http://smap.landcareresearch.co.nz>
- Soil Bureau Bulletin 27 – General Survey of the soils of the South Island, New Zealand, DSIR 1968. Maps 1,3,5,7,8 relate to Buller/Westland.

Ministry for Primary Industries (MPI) Sustainable Farming Fund (SFF) projects:

Website: <http://archive.mpi.govt.nz/applications/sustainable-farming-fund-search>

- 03/126: Solutions to nutrient runoff from West Coast land conversion.
- 05/047: Improved nutrient management systems for dairy farming in high rainfall areas (Inchbonnie Catchment).
- 06/064: Characterising soil nutrient accumulation and loss from dairy farm pastures on the West Coast (Lake Brunner).
- 07/143: Best management practices to optimise nutrient use efficiency on modified soils of the South Island West Coast.
- 09/080: Manuka beetle control in West Coast pastures.
- 11/091: Efficient fertiliser use on humps & hollows on the West Coast.
- 401443: Pest management in land use modification on the South Island West Coast.

Further reading:

- Horrocks AJ, Thomas SM, Tregurtha CS, Beare MH, Meenken ED 2010. Implications for dry matter production and N management as soils develop following 'humping and hollowing' on the West Coast. Proceedings of the New Zealand Grassland Association 72: 103–108.
- McDowell RW 2008a. Phosphorus in humped and hollowed soils of the Inchbonnie catchment, West Coast, New Zealand: I. Variation with age and distribution. New Zealand Journal of Agricultural Research 51(3): 299–306.
- McDowell RW 2008b. Phosphorus in humped and hollowed soils of the Inchbonnie catchment, West Coast, New Zealand: II. Accounting for losses by different pathways. New Zealand Journal of Agricultural Research 51(3): 307–316.
- Thomas SM, Beare MH, Ford CD, Rietveld V 2007. Changes in soil quality following humping/hollowing and flipping of pakihi soils on the West Coast, South Island, New Zealand. Proceedings of the New Zealand Grassland Association 69: 265–270.

APPENDIX C – LAND DEVELOPMENT PLANNING CHECKLIST

Step	To do	Outcome / Issues
1	Advice Talk to as many people as possible.	
2	Resource Management Act Do you need resource consent or not?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact the WCRC • See Appendix A
3	Development plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw up a farm plan or use a farm map to mark on important land features
4	Aerial photographs and maps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtain a copy of an aerial photo and/or map from WCRC or online (Chapter 4.4)
5	Drainage Where does the water currently drain on the farm? Will you need new culverts or drains?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mark drainage features onto farm plan • Mark new culvert or drain locations onto farm plan
6	Paddock size and fence clearing Think about the total area of the farm and how it will be laid out.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide how many paddocks you want • Draw paddocks onto farm plan • Remove old fencing and price new fencing
7	Stock access and water troughs Where will you locate your gateways and water troughs?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mark gateways and water troughs onto farm plan

Step	To do	Outcome / Issues
8 Effluent Where will effluent be stored/disposed?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mark on plan where subsurface pipes and hydrants will be located 	
9 Sediment control and silt traps How will these be constructed?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mark silt traps onto farm plan 	
10 Vegetation Do you need to clear? What will this cost? How will you do it?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mark on farm plan riparian strips or wetland areas that should be fenced off 	
11 Impact on farm system Think through the flow-on effects on stocking rate and farm infrastructure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farm tracks, shed, new stock 	
12 Consultation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform neighbours about your development plan 	
13 Ongoing cost and budgeting Factor in ongoing costs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss with accountant, bank manager Weeds, pests, reseeding, slumping, extra N 	
14 Timing When will the work be done? Who will do it?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Talk to contractors Source seed, lime, fertiliser 	

